

**A mathematical exploration/ A study of
population dynamics**
**For how long can the earth sustain
human population growth?**

Math Analysis and Approaches SL Internal Assessment

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Introduction

Earth. A planet that houses 7,794,799 thousand humans and *growing* (United Nations, 2019). I for one have always been fascinated by Earth's ability to support life for Eons and that has allured me to wonder; But for how long? For how long can this giving planet sustain such growth?

Thomas Malthus, an influential British cleric, scholar, and economist in the fields of political economy and demography best known for the Theory of Population; challenged the persisting notion that population could grow unfettered; hence, Malthus believed in *scarcity*, a simple economic concept which revolves around limited resources; in particular; finite food, space, natural resources, etc. However, the model he proposed was somewhat flawed given its exponential nature. That is where P.F. Verhulst, a distinguished Belgian mathematician interceded to build on the Malthusian model to better portray this so-called environmental ceiling; proposed by Malthus; thus, nurturing what is called; the Logistic growth model. A model which accounts for the parameter that is the carrying capacity ~ a maximum imposed by limited resource availability.

Such reality has invoked me to wonder how such model applies to the entirety of the human population as opposed to a single population. Moreover, conclusions arrived at will shed light on the earth's current growth rate as well as a relative measure of the current population with respect to the earth's carrying capacity thus elucidating when measures must irrefutably be taken to avoid hitting carrying capacity which may be catastrophic.

Methodology

I will begin by collecting population data from 1950 to 2020 from the United Nations database. I'll then solve the Malthusian differential equation as to arrive at the Malthusian function thus founding a base to solve the logistic differential equation. Next, I'll obtain the parameters necessary for the logistic function using excel. Aided by technology I'll be solving the logistic function for ascribed time intervals to accurately model world population. Subsequently, using technology, statistical measures will be used to measure the accuracy of values obtained from the logistic model in comparison to the population data extracted from the United Nations database. Successively, I'll be using graphing software to graph the logistic function and plot real

population against estimated population and the carrying capacity. Finally, I'll attempt to answer the question of 'For how long can the earth sustain human population growth?'.

Data collection

Below is the world population adapted from the United Nations database. It must be noted that said values are estimates:

Year	Total population (thousands)
1950	2,536,431
1955	2,773,020
1960	3,040,950
1965	3,339,584
1970	3,700,437
1975	4,079,480
1980	4,458,003
1985	4,870,922
1990	5,372,231
1995	5,744,213
2000	6,143,494
2005	6,541,907
2010	6,956,824
2015	7,379,797
2020	7,794,799

Figure 1. Total Population – Both sexes (*United Nations, 2019*)

The reason I've chosen the year range 1950-2020 is primarily due to availability of data online. In addition, I've chosen a 5-year increment as a 1-year increment would imply dealing with 70 single time intervals, while a 10-year increment is perhaps too generalistic in context of the world population; thus, a 5-year increment is rather ideal.

Now that the necessary data has been obtained, the Malthusian model is to be embarked upon, such that a base is built to subsequently discern the logistic model.

The Malthusian model

The Malthusian model (*Khan, Growth models: introduction, 2018*) expresses exponential growth such that a population's per capita growth rate (r) remains constant regardless of population density (P). Thus, the two preliminary variables are:

P – Population

r – Growth rate per capita (proportionality constant)

So how can one model the rate of change of population with respect to time?

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = rP$$

The differential equation above states that the rate of change of population with respect to time is proportional to the growth rate per capita x the population itself.

It is important to stress that in exponential growth; if population density is smaller, then minimal change per unit time will result as population density increases; meanwhile if population density is larger, then maximal change per unit time will result.

We now must solve $\frac{dP}{dt} = rP$ to derive a function (the exponential function)

To solve said differential equation (first order), separation of variables is used
First divide both sides by P and multiply both sides by dt

$$\frac{1}{P} dP = r dt$$

Take the anti-derivative of both sides

$$\int \frac{1}{P} dP = \int r dt$$

$$\ln|P| = rt + C$$

Now solve for P bearing in mind that $|P|$ will always be positive and hence can simply be rewritten as P

$$P = e^{rt+C}$$

$$P = e^{rt} e^C$$

e^C is essentially an arbitrary constant which can be rewritten as C

$$P = C e^{rt}$$

$$P(t) = C e^{rt}$$

Notice, the above function satisfies the differential equation $\frac{dP}{dt} = rP$

Let us now set some initial conditions

1-

$$P(0) = P_0$$

2-

$$P(0) = C e^0$$

$$P(0) = C$$

Thus, the final exponential growth function is:

$$P(t) = P_0 e^{rt}$$

It is imperative to clarify that the exponential model is illogical and non-conforming to reality given one major flaw; the models' domain and range such that the domain is all real numbers, and the range is all real numbers greater than 0. In application this set of conditions insinuate that the population (as defined by the exponential function $P(t) = P_0 e^{rt}$) can grow unfettered for eternity which is simply impossible given Earth's resources are finite and scarce. However, the

Malthusian model serves as an essential building block to the Logistic model which accounts for said finiteness and scarcity.

The logistic model

The logistic model (*Khan, The logistic growth model, 2018*) introduces a new variable; the carrying capacity (k), such that the equation is bounded by finiteness/scarcity. Thus, the logistic differential equation takes the form:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = rP \left(1 - \frac{P}{k}\right)$$

You may have noticed that what Verhulst has done is essentially constrain Malthus' model such that when P is substantially smaller than k , $\left(1 - \frac{P}{k}\right)$ is going to approach 1. Meanwhile, as P approaches k , $\left(1 - \frac{P}{k}\right)$ is going to approach 0. In application, as population density approaches the carrying capacity the population growth rate $\frac{dP}{dt}$ approaches 0 meanwhile; if the population is a small fraction of the carrying capacity, then the population growth rate $\frac{dP}{dt}$ is equal to rP (exponential).

Permutations

Permutation 1 $\sim P(t) = 0$

If $P_0 = 0$ then $\frac{dP}{dt} = 0$. In application this means that if at time 0 the population is 0, then the population growth rate will remain at 0 forever. Thus, satisfying the differential equation under study.

Permutation 2 $\sim P(t) = k$

If $P_0 = k$ then $\frac{dP}{dt} = 0$. In application this means that if at time 0 the population is equal to the carrying capacity, then the population growth rate will remain at 0

forever (population density will remain constant at k). Thus, satisfying the differential equation under study.

Permutation 3 $\sim 0 < P_0 < k$

If P is a small fraction of k , rP will be the dominant constituent, thus its rate of increase increases as P increases (the rate of change is going to grow rather exponentially). However, as P approaches k , $(1 - \frac{P}{k})$ will dictate the rate of change, thus its rate of increase decreases as P increases (essentially asymptote towards k). Resulting in somewhat of a S-shaped curve.

Pay close attention to permutation 3 as that is the behavior we seek to model

We now must solve $\frac{dP}{dt} = rP(1 - \frac{P}{k})$ to derive a function (the logistic function)

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = rP(1 - \frac{P}{k})$$

To solve said differential equation (ODE), *separation of variables* is used
Divide both sides by $P(1 - \frac{P}{k})$ and multiply both sides by dt

$$\frac{1}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} dP = r dt$$

To find the antiderivative of both sides we first must expand the fraction on the left-hand side using *partial fraction expansion* such that

$$\frac{1}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} = \frac{A}{P} + \frac{B}{1 - \frac{P}{k}}$$

Next, sum up the right hand-side

Cross-multiply the two fractions and add the results together then multiply the two denominators (adding fractions with unlike denominators)

$$\frac{1}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} = \frac{A - \frac{A}{k}P + BP}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})}$$

Attempt to find A and B, notice we have a constant term (1) on the left hand-side and no P thus we can add 0P to the left hand-side

$$\frac{1 + 0P}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} = \frac{A - \frac{A}{k}P + BP}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})}$$

Hence $A = 1$ meanwhile $-\frac{A}{k} + B = 0$

Solve for B

$$B = \frac{1}{k}$$

Now rewrite the equation given A and B

$$\frac{1}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} = \frac{A}{P} + \frac{B}{1 - \frac{P}{k}}$$

$$\frac{1}{P(1 - \frac{P}{k})} = \frac{1}{P} + \frac{\frac{1}{k}}{1 - \frac{P}{k}}$$

The equation is now ready to integrate

$$\frac{1}{P} + \frac{\frac{1}{k}}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} dP = r dt$$

$$\int \frac{1}{P} + \frac{\frac{1}{k}}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} dP = \int r dt$$

Separate the integral

$$\int \frac{1}{P} dP + \int \frac{\frac{1}{k}}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} dP = \int r dt$$

Pull the constant out of the integral

$$\int \frac{1}{P} dP + \frac{1}{k} \int \frac{1}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} dP = \int r dt$$

$\int \frac{1}{P} dP$ is simply $\ln|P|$

Apply u substitution to $\int \frac{1}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} dP$

$$\text{let } u = 1 - \frac{P}{k}$$

$$\int \frac{1}{u} dP$$

$$\frac{du}{dP} = -\frac{1}{k}$$
$$dP = -k du$$

$$\int \frac{1}{u} - k du$$

$$-k \int \frac{1}{u} du$$

$$-k \ln|u|$$

$$-k \ln \left| 1 - \frac{P}{k} \right|$$

For simplicity moving onwards, rewrite as:

$$\frac{\ln \left| 1 - \frac{P}{k} \right|}{-\frac{1}{k}}$$

Hence, the full expression is:

$$\ln|P| + \frac{1}{k} \frac{\ln \left| 1 - \frac{P}{k} \right|}{-\frac{1}{k}}$$

Cancel $+\frac{1}{k}$ with $-\frac{1}{k}$

$$\ln|P| - \ln \left| 1 - \frac{P}{k} \right|$$

$\int r dt$ is simply $rt + C$ given we add the constant of integration on the right hand-side

Proceed to writing the entire integrated equation

$$\ln|P| - \ln \left| 1 - \frac{P}{k} \right| = rt + C$$

Assume $0 < P(t) < k$ such that P is always positive (refer to permutation 3)

Replace absolute value brackets with parenthesis

$$\ln(P) - \ln \left(1 - \frac{P}{k} \right) = rt + C$$

Use logarithm properties to rewrite the left-hand side such that the logarithm of the first expression divided by the logarithm of the second expression is

$$\ln\left(\frac{P}{1 - \frac{P}{k}}\right) = rt + C$$

Get rid of the natural log

$$\frac{P}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} = e^{rt+C}$$

$$\frac{P}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} = e^{rt} e^C$$

e^C is essentially an arbitrary constant which can be rewritten as C

$$\frac{P}{1 - \frac{P}{k}} = C e^{rt}$$

Solve for P

Take the reciprocal of both sides

$$\frac{1 - \frac{P}{k}}{P} = \frac{1}{C e^{+rt}}$$

Again $\frac{1}{C}$ is a constant which can be rewritten as C such that

$$\frac{1 - \frac{P}{k}}{P} = C e^{-rt}$$

Divide the left hand-side by P

$$\frac{1}{P} - \frac{1}{k} = C e^{-rt}$$

Add $-\frac{1}{k}$ to both sides

$$\frac{1}{P} = Ce^{-rt} + \frac{1}{k}$$

To solve for P simply take the reciprocal of both sides

$$P(t) = \frac{1}{Ce^{-rt} + \frac{1}{k}}$$

Assumptions/ initial conditions to solve for C

$$P(0) = P_0$$

$$P(0) = \frac{1}{Ce^0 + \frac{1}{k}} = P_0$$

$$P(0) = \frac{1}{C + \frac{1}{k}} = P_0$$

Once more take the reciprocal of both sides

$$C + \frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{P_0}$$

Subtract $+\frac{1}{k}$ from both sides

$$C = \frac{1}{P_0} - \frac{1}{k}$$

We can now rewrite the solution (the logistic function)

$$P(t) = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{P_0} - \frac{1}{k}\right)e^{-rt} + \frac{1}{k}}$$

To simplify multiply the numerator and denominator by P_0k

$$P(t) = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{P_0} - \frac{1}{k}\right)e^{-rt} + \frac{1}{k}} \times \frac{P_0k}{P_0k}$$

$$P(t) = \frac{P_0k}{(k - P_0)e^{-rt} + P_0}$$

And that is the solution to the logistic differential equation also known as *the logistic function*. Thus, the logistic model shall now be used to model world population growth, but first a set of parameters must first be obtained.

Obtaining parameters for the logistic model

There are 2 primary parameters to obtain:

- 1- r ~ the growth rate per capita
- 2- k ~ the carrying capacity

Let us start with k

Malthus states ‘The power of population is so superior to the power of the Earth to produce subsistence for man, that premature death must in some shape or other visit the human race.’ (Smith, 2015). But what ‘power of population’ is enough to top Earth’s power to produce subsistence for man; alternatively stated what is Earth’s carrying capacity?

One scientist; namely, Edward O. Wilson (Harvard University sociobiologist) who bases his estimate on calculations of the Earth's available resources claims that the Earth’s carrying capacity is 10 billion humans (Wolchover, 2011).

$$k = 10,000,000,000$$

Or

$$k = 10^{10}$$

With regards to r

We first must clarify the time intervals understudy

Year	Time intervals (years)
1950	0
1955	5
1960	10
1965	15
1970	20
1975	25
1980	30

1985	35
1990	40
1995	45
2000	50
2005	55
2010	60
2015	65
2020	70

To calculate the r value, it's a matter of substituting the actual population and relative time interval into the logistic model. Below is an example of the r value for the time interval (5):

$$P(t) = \frac{P_0 k}{(k - P_0)e^{-rt} + P_0}$$

$$P(5) = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-r(5)} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

$$2,773,020 \times 10^3 = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{(7,463,569 \times 10^3)e^{-r(5)} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

$$\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{2,773,020 \times 10^3} = (7,463,569 \times 10^3)e^{-r(5)} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)$$

$$\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{2,773,020 \times 10^3} - (2,536,431 \times 10^3) = (7,463,569 \times 10^3)e^{-r(5)}$$

$$\frac{\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{2,773,020 \times 10^3} - (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}{(7,463,569 \times 10^3)} = e^{-r(5)}$$

$$\ln \frac{\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{2,773,020 \times 10^3} - (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}{(7,463,569 \times 10^3)} = -5r$$

$$\ln \frac{\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{2,773,020 \times 10^3} - (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}{(7,463,569 \times 10^3)} = r$$

$$r = 0.02427829547$$

However, such tedious process will be carried out on excel for the remaining 13 r values, but in order to do so we must first rearrange the equation in terms of r:

$$P(t) = \frac{P_0 k}{(k - P_0)e^{-rt} + P_0}$$

$$\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} = (k - P_0)e^{-rt} + P_0$$

$$\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} = (k - P_0)e^{-rt} + P_0$$

$$\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0 = (k - P_0)e^{-rt}$$

$$\frac{\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0}{(k - P_0)} = e^{-rt}$$

$$\ln \frac{\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0}{(k - P_0)} = -rt$$

$$\ln \frac{\frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0}{(k - P_0)} = -rt$$

$$\frac{\ln \frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0}{(k - P_0) - t} = r$$

Next generate a table on excel (t vs. P(t)) ~ (time vs. relative population) and set up the derived equation (call it the r equation) on the excel function module and let excel do its magic!

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	t	P(t)	r						
2	0	2,536,431,000	N/A	average					
3	5	2,773,020,000	$\ln((2536431000*10000000000/83 - 2536431000)/(10000000000 - 2536431000))/-A3$	0.02930686					
4	10	3,040,950,000	0.025140274						
5	15	3,339,584,000	0.025929336						
6	20	3,700,437,000	0.02736232						
7	25	4,079,480,000	0.02827284						
8	30	4,458,003,000	0.028720725						
9	35	4,870,922,000	0.029360945						
10	40	5,372,231,000	0.030711103						
11	45	5,744,213,000	0.030648643						
12	50	6,143,494,000	0.030898156						
13	55	6,541,907,000	0.031214312						
14	60	6,956,824,000	0.031768285						
15	65	7,379,797,000	0.032534924						
16	70	7,794,799,000	0.033455911						

$$\frac{\ln \frac{P_0 k}{P(t)} - P_0}{(k - P_0) - t} = r$$

Note that once all r values are resolved, we find their average using the AVG function. We do so such that the r value represents the growth rate of the entirety of the time interval as opposed to a single time interval. Hence the final r value is:

$$r = 0.02936862$$

Substitute the final r value to arrive at the final equation:

$$P(t) = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-(0.029306862)t} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

Solving for P(t)

Now that all parameters have been obtained, it's a simple matter of substituting said time intervals into logistic function as to solve for P(t). E.g.

$$P(5) = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-(0.029306862)(5)} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

$$P(5) = 2823688683$$

To calculate the remaining population values we'll once more be using excel:

- 1- Set up the final logistic function using the excel function module as follows:

SUM								
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	t	r		t	r(AVG)	P(t)		
2		0 N/A		0	0.02930686	2536431000))		
3	5	0.0242783		5		2,823,688,683		
4	10	0.02514027		10		3,129,836,532		
5	15	0.02592934		15		3,453,205,042		
6	20	0.02736232		20		3,791,544,957		
7	25	0.02827284		25		4,142,061,369		
8	30	0.02872072		30		4,501,487,055		
9	35	0.02936094		35		4,866,193,024		
10	40	0.0307111		40		5,232,329,419		
11	45	0.03064864		45		5,595,985,728		
12	50	0.03089816		50		5,953,356,381		
13	55	0.03121431		55		6,300,897,048		
14	60	0.03176828		60		6,635,458,291		
15	65	0.03253492		65		6,954,386,572		
16	70	0.03345591		70		7,255,587,025		
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								

$P(t) = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-(0.029306862)t} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$	
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- 2- Replicate the function for each value of t as displayed above as to obtain P(t) for all remaining time intervals
- 3- We now must compare the estimated population (logistic) vs the actual population (UN) to measure the accuracy of the model, we do this using the regression model; precisely, the coefficient of determination or simply put the r^2 value which represents 'the proportion of the variance for a variable (the logistic population) that's explained by another variable (the real population)' (Bloomenthal, 2019) and has the equation:

$$r^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{RES}}{SS_{TOT}} = 1 - \frac{\sum_i (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

However, such operation will be carried out using the RSQ excel function:

H2 =RSQ(F2:F16,G2:G16)								
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	t	r		t	r(AVG)	P(t)	Actual P(t)	r^2
2		0 N/A		0	0.02930686	2,536,431,000	2,536,431,000	0.99750652
3		5 0.0242783		5		2,823,688,683	2,773,020,000	
4		10 0.02514027		10		3,129,836,532	3,040,950,000	
5		15 0.02592934		15		3,453,205,042	3,339,584,000	
6		20 0.02736232		20		3,791,544,957	3,700,437,000	
7		25 0.02827284		25		4,142,061,369	4,079,480,000	
8		30 0.02872072		30		4,501,487,055	4,458,003,000	
9		35 0.02936094		35		4,866,193,024	4,870,922,000	
10		40 0.0307111		40		5,232,329,419	5,372,231,000	
11		45 0.03064864		45		5,595,985,728	5,744,213,000	
12		50 0.03089816		50		5,953,356,381	6,143,494,000	
13		55 0.03121431		55		6,300,897,048	6,541,907,000	
14		60 0.03176828		60		6,635,458,291	6,956,824,000	
15		65 0.03253492		65		6,954,386,572	7,379,797,000	
16		70 0.03345591		70		7,255,587,025	7,794,799,000	
17								
18								
19								
20								
21								

$$P(t) = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-(0.029306862)t} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

We are left with an r^2 value:

$$r^2 = 0.997506522$$

Indicating that 99.75% of the variance of the dependent variable (logistic population) is explained by the independent variable (real population) in the

regression model. The r^2 value lies between 0 and 1, hence indicating strong positive correlation. Proving that the model is indeed valid.

Modelling logistic world population growth

1- First enter the equation as is using the ' $f(x)$ expression' tool

2- Fix the v-window such that:

y -min = 0, though 0 is not the initial population, we know that even afore time interval 0, population could not have dropped below 0 humans.

y -max = $1.1 \cdot 10^{10}$, recall 10^{10} is earth's carrying capacity and is essentially the ceiling, hence 1.1 allows us to view the desired portion of the y -axis freely.

x -min = -100, though the selected population starts at time interval 0, -100 permits us to read population afore 1950.

x -max = 1050, which is the year 3000 from the starting point that is 1950 allowing us to view the desired s-shaped curve of the logistic curve

3- Next insert a table with an x column (t) and an F(x) column P(t). Fill in the x column with the predetermined time intervals and Desmos will computationally draw out the F(x) values from the graph.

- 4- Insert a table containing the real population to compare estimated population and real population graphically; Plot variable x (t) against variable y ($P(t)$) and manually fill in both the x column and y column accordingly.

Notice how the values graphically derived on Desmos exactly match the ones derived systematically on excel!

5- Graph the carrying capacity K to visualize the horizontal asymptote

Set $y = 10^{10}$

The final verdict

As previously stated, the logistic model is an asymptotic model given its tendency to continually approach the carrying capacity such that the horizontal asymptote is 10 billion ($y = 10^{10}$). Hence, the curve can never intersect said limit but rather infinitely approach it. Below is a visualization of the asymptotic nature of the logistic model:

To confirm we conduct the following calculation:

$$10^{10} = \frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{((10^{10}) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3))e^{-(0.029306862)t} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)}$$

$$\frac{(2,536,431 \times 10^3) \times (10^{10})}{10^{10}} = (7,463,569 \times 10^3)e^{-(0.029306862)t} + (2,536,431 \times 10^3)$$

$$(2,536,431 \times 10^3) - (2,536,431 \times 10^3) = (7,463,569 \times 10^3)e^{-(0.029306862)t}$$

$$\frac{0}{(7,463,569 \times 10^3)} = e^{-(0.029306862)t}$$

$$\ln 0 = - (0.029306862)t$$

$$\frac{\ln 0}{-(0.029306862)} = t$$

$$t = \text{Ma ERROR}$$

Limitations

It is apparent that once the population experiences a decreasing rate of increase (approaching carrying capacity) the model becomes unsound. Such limitation has surfaced in an attempt to attain an approximated answer to said question. Through equating $P(t) = 9,999,999,999$ such that $\ln 0$ does not hold and solving for (t) the answer is anomalous ($t = 822.5$ years). To confirm I tested for $P(t) = 9,999,999,990$ such that ($t = 743.9$); a difference of 78.6 years for an increase of 9 humans! Adversely when solving for $P(t)$ given t, at increased time intervals, the function displays increases of very small fractions (e.g. quarter a human being). Which is simply non-viable.

On a general note, limitations of this exploration include the assumption of carrying capacity, in addition to the utilization of a single set of 'real' population (extracted from the UN database) as opposed to an average of a set of databases. However, the main limitation is perhaps the method of extracting an r value where the r value could have been more reflective of the 'real' growth rate.

Conclusion

Fascinated by Earth's ability to support life for Eons, I have successfully dismantled the exponential and logistic models further manipulating the logistic model to accurately portray human population growth.

In conclusion, it can be discerned that the logistic model is rather inconclusive in addressing the question 'For how long can the earth sustain human population growth' where by nature, the model does not intersect the carrying capacity. However, what can be ascertained is the following: the human population is currently facing an increasing rate of increase given by the calculated r^2 value as well as the population's operation on the exponential portion of the logistic curve. On a final note, such exploration has ignited a spark in me towards such dynamic studies precisely ones that aid in prediction and are grounded on human phenomena. Moreover, such exploration has allowed me to explore extended mathematical principles namely, ordinary differential equations; precisely those of the first order in addition to concepts such as separation of variables as well as partial fraction expansion.

Reflection

According to my calculations, as of the end of 2021 ($t = 71$) our population rests at 7,313,556,456 and according to the UNFPA (United Nations Populations Fund) our population rests at 7,875,000,000 (*UNFPA, 2021*), which approximately equates to 73.14% and 78.75% of earth's carrying capacity respectively, hence one should be wary of such statistics and virtually gain control of them by way of worldly cooperation in order to preserve the planet that has provided sustenance for eons.

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